

Constrained Governance: A Heuristic Analogy Between Political Decision-Makers and Solvers of Differential-Algebraic Equations

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Abstract

Why do some rigid regimes collapse when confronted with similar shocks, while others resist or stabilize? Although classical approaches explain institutional vulnerability, they often struggle to account for divergent crisis trajectories. This article proposes a heuristic analogy between political governance and the numerical simulation of differential-algebraic equations (DAEs).

Within this analogy, the DAE index is not treated as a direct measure of numerical stiffness, but rather as a metaphor for the degree of coupling, lock-in, and hierarchical organization of institutional constraints within decision-making processes. Explicit and implicit solvers are used to characterize two contrasting modes of political decision-making: reactive and sequential action on the one hand, and integrative and simultaneous management of constraints, on the other.

From an exploratory perspective, four comparative cases illustrate the proposed framework: Algeria's Black Decade, the Arab Spring, the Algerian Hirak, and the escalation involving the United States, Israel, and Iran between 2023 and 2026. The analysis suggests that the trajectory of regimes or systems in crisis depends less on structural rigidity alone than on the degree of fit between their level of institutional constraint and the mode of decision-making they adopt. The framework remains non-predictive and is intended primarily as a conceptual language for thinking about institutional resilience, constraint-related drift, and political rupture.

Keywords: constrained governance; stiff governance; differential-algebraic equations; DAE; constrained systems; political index; explicit solver; implicit solver; constraint residual; political crises; institutional resilience; algorithmic competence

1. Introduction

Many geopolitical systems appear stable until a marginal shock triggers a major crisis. Structural approaches, informed by chaos theory, explain this general fragility in terms of sensitivity to initial conditions. Yet they remain insufficient to explain why structurally similar regimes follow divergent trajectories when exposed to comparable pressures.

This article builds on earlier work on the simulation of constrained systems through DAEs (Zaatri & Azzizi, 2018; Zaatri, 2026) in order to propose a dynamic reading of sociopolitical

crises centered on decision-making processes. Drawing inspiration from the numerical simulation of constrained multibody mechanical systems, it approaches geopolitical crises as problems of governance under constraints.

The proposed analogy relies in particular on the notion of index k , borrowed from differential-algebraic systems. In the context of DAEs, the index refers to the degree to which system dynamics and algebraic constraints are intertwined. Transposed into the political domain, it is used here in a strictly heuristic sense to designate the degree of interdependence, lock-in, and hierarchical organization of institutional constraints within decision-making processes. The argument therefore does not posit any formal equivalence between DAEs and political regimes; rather, it proposes a functional analogy between the numerical analysis of constrained systems and the mechanisms of political governance.

2. State of the Art: From Structure to Functional Dynamics

Since the twentieth century, chaos theory has shown that certain nonlinear systems may undergo abrupt shifts under minor perturbations through bifurcations or hysteresis. Scholars such as Lorenz (1995), Thom (1972), Zeeman (1976), and Jervis (1997) have applied these insights to the social sciences in order to understand the fragility of political regimes and the way weak signals can trigger major strategic ruptures. Nevertheless, these approaches remain largely descriptive. They tend to treat institutions as relatively static structures rather than as dynamic processes shaped by conflicting constraints.

Even existing mathematical models, such as Jones and Baumgartner's (2005) work on political attention or Cederman's (2003) simulations of war size, remain limited in their ability to capture complex decision-making processes in real time. The literature is thus still marked by weak formalization of constraint dynamics and limited empirical validation.

Against this background, it is worth developing hybrid frameworks that combine structural diagnosis with dynamic analysis. The approach proposed here rests on an analogy with the numerical simulation of constrained systems governed by DAEs, in which stability depends on the fit between system structure, degree of constraint, and the choice of solver (Ascher & Petzold, 1998).

3. Governance as a Constrained Dynamical System

3.1 From Structure to Functional Process

Conventional approaches focus primarily on the nature of institutions and political regimes. Although complexity theory has enriched this perspective, it remains chiefly descriptive. It does not adequately explain how actors manage, in real time, the conflicts and constraints they face. This article instead proposes a functional perspective in which governance is understood as a dynamic process of continuously resolving competing constraints. From this standpoint, system stability depends on the capacity of the "solver" to resolve the constrained problem effectively. This perspective resonates both with the literature on adaptive governance (Folke et al., 2005) and with research on decision-making under crisis conditions (Boin et al., 2016).

It is important to emphasize that this approach is grounded in a heuristic analogy. Political regimes cannot be assimilated to DAE systems in any strict mathematical sense. Their decision-

making dynamics can, however, be usefully compared to those of constrained systems, in which stability depends on the simultaneous handling of multiple constraints. The analogy thus constitutes neither a structural equivalence nor a rigorous predictive model.

The term “solver” refers here to the mode of decision-making adopted by the governing authority of a state or by a hegemonic power. It designates the ensemble of structures and authority mechanisms through which constraints are arbitrated and decisions implemented. Constraints refer to the full set of conditions to which a political system is subject and which it must incorporate and respect in order to function. These include institutional and constitutional rules, internal balances of power, and the social, economic, and geopolitical pressures that shape political action. In this sense, “algorithmic competence” refers to the decision-maker’s ability to assess heuristically the level of constraint confronting the system and to select a mode of resolution suited to both the institutional structure and the crisis context.

3.2 The DAE Heuristic: Index, Institutional Constraint, and Regime Typology

In the classical mathematical definition, the index k denotes the number of differentiations required to transform a DAE system into an equivalent ordinary differential or semi-explicit form. It should be stressed, however, that the index k is not a direct measure of numerical stiffness. Numerical stiffness instead refers to stability difficulties associated with the coexistence of sharply divergent timescales within the same system. In practice, high-index DAE systems are often harder to solve because their constraints are more tightly embedded in the system’s overall dynamics (Ascher & Petzold, 1998).

Within the present analogy, a high political index characterizes a regime in which institutional lock-in leaves decision-makers with very limited room for maneuver. Each action undertaken by the system is tightly constrained by an entanglement of historical, legal, and social constraints. Governance under constraints thus arises when the political solver attempts to preserve the stability of a high-index system without possessing the integration tools required to do so. Under such conditions, the risk of adjustment errors increases and abrupt breakdowns become more likely.

In this article, the index k is used exclusively as a heuristic notion. It is not an empirically measurable quantitative indicator, but a conceptual device intended to represent the degree of institutional constraint within a political system. A political system with a high index is therefore not simply one subject to many constraints.

Rather, it is a system in which constraints are interdependent, difficult to modify separately, and liable to generate cascading effects when decisions are made without sufficient coordination. By contrast, a low-index system possesses more flexible mechanisms capable of absorbing, negotiating, or correcting imbalances without immediately precipitating a crisis affecting the system as a whole.

Within this analogy, the values $k \geq 3$, $k \approx 2$, and $k \leq 1$ should not be interpreted as precise cardinal measures. They merely designate typological classes intended to compare different political configurations.

Systems with a high political index ($k \geq 3$)—such as highly centralized authoritarian regimes, totalitarian systems, or certain closed bureaucracies—are characterized by tightly interwoven

constraints. They are typically marked by rigid ideology, strong centralization of decision-making, weak institutional autonomy, restrictions on civil liberties, and a limited capacity for internal adjustment. In such systems, abrupt or poorly coordinated decisions can generate cumulative drift. Constraints that are ignored or neglected do not disappear; they are displaced, accumulate, and eventually reappear in the form of crisis.

Systems with a medium political index ($k \approx 2$)—such as certain hegemonic powers or regimes deeply embedded in alliance networks—must navigate and arbitrate among multiple constraints. They must take into account international commitments, strategic alliances, public opinion, international legality, security requirements, and economic stability. In this type of configuration, unilateral coercive action does not necessarily increase the index in the strict sense, but it may increase the constraint residual, that is, the gap between decisions taken and the institutional, legal, or geopolitical constraints that the system is supposed to integrate and uphold.

Systems with a low political index ($k \leq 1$)—such as consolidated democracies or regimes with more flexible institutions—generally benefit from more numerous and better-developed mechanisms of correction, negotiation, and adjustment. Such systems can tolerate greater temporary deviations because institutional processes often allow errors or imbalances to be corrected before they evolve into systemic crises.

This clarification helps avoid any direct conflation of the DAE index with political rigidity. The central argument is rather that a system subject to strong constraints requires a mode of decision-making capable of simultaneously accounting for multiple interdependent and dynamically entangled constraints. In that sense, the fit between a system's political index and the type of decision-making solver it employs becomes a crucial variable.

3.3 The Core of the Analogy: Explicit vs. Implicit Solver

The stability of a DAE simulation depends not only on the type of solver used, but also on the fit between the system's structure, its level of constraint, and the method of resolution chosen. This relation of fit lies at the core of the analogy developed in this article.

An explicit solver advances the system's dynamics from its current state and only subsequently corrects deviations from the constraints when necessary. Transposed into the political domain, this logic corresponds to a reactive, sequential, and often coercive mode of governance. In this mode of decision-making, action is taken before the full range of institutional, social, or geopolitical constraints has been adequately incorporated. In the face of popular protest, for instance, such an approach may privilege emergency measures, immediate repression, diplomatic ultimatums, or preemptive military action. Action thus precedes the full integration of constraints and the consequences it may produce.

An implicit solver, by contrast, enforces constraint satisfaction at each stage of the computation. Transposed into politics, this logic corresponds to an anticipatory, negotiated, and integrative approach. Decisions are elaborated by taking into account, from the outset and simultaneously, social, institutional, economic, and geopolitical constraints. Such an approach is generally slower and more resource-intensive, but it limits drift and reduces the risk of systemic rupture.

From this perspective, a regime's vulnerability does not depend solely on its degree of institutional rigidity. It stems from a mismatch between the level of constraint to which the system is subject and the mode of decision-making adopted. Thus, when a high-index political system is governed through an explicit solver, it becomes especially vulnerable to the accumulation of constraint residuals and, consequently, to trajectories of crisis, escalation, or breakdown.

4. Mechanisms of Functional Breakdown and General Hypotheses

4.1 Hypothesis 1: Mismatch between Political Index and Decision-Making Mode

A system characterized by a high political index becomes particularly vulnerable when it operates through an explicit decision-making mode. In such a configuration, decisions are taken reactively and sequentially, without the simultaneous integration of institutional, social, and geopolitical constraints. This mismatch may lead to the gradual accumulation of constraint residuals, thereby fueling a loss of regime legitimacy, the radicalization of actors, and, in some cases, institutional breakdown.

4.2 Hypothesis 2: Rapid Shock and the Amplification of Constraint Residuals

When a rapid shock affects a highly constrained system—whether in the form of economic crisis, popular mobilization, military conflict, or international pressure—the use of an explicit solver may amplify instability. Uncoordinated emergency responses, coercive measures, or unilateral decisions may temporarily alleviate immediate pressure, but they often increase the gap between the decisions adopted and the constraints the system is supposed to integrate. That gap is interpreted here as a political constraint residual.

4.3 Hypothesis 3: Stabilization through Implicit Decision-Making

Conversely, when confronted with the same type of shock, the use of an implicit mode of decision-making may favor relative stabilization. Prior consultation, negotiation, gradual adjustment, and the simultaneous consideration of multiple constraints all help limit the accumulation of constraint residuals. This approach is slower and more costly, but it better preserves the regime's room for maneuver and reduces the risk of immediate rupture. These hypotheses should be understood as heuristic rather than law-like. Their purpose is to structure the comparative analysis of the cases examined, not to establish general or universal causal laws.

5. Illustrative Case Studies: The Solver Confronted with Events

The cases presented below, drawn from recent historical episodes or developments still underway, do not constitute empirical validation in the statistical sense. Rather, they function as comparative illustrations intended to assess the descriptive coherence of the proposed framework, without any claim to generalization or any intention to establish definitive causal relationships. The analysis focuses exclusively on decision-making mechanisms and does not seek to pass judgment on the legality or legitimacy of the actions undertaken by the actors concerned.

5.1 Algeria's Black Decade (1990s): Breakdown under an Explicit Solver

Faced with the first mobilizations in Algiers, the regime—characterized by strong centralization of power and a one-party system—responded with a strategy of immediate coercion, marked in particular by military repression and the interruption of the electoral process following the first round of the December 1991 legislative elections.

This strategy, characteristic of an explicit decision-making mode, was poorly suited to a highly constrained system marked by a high political index. Deep sociopolitical constraints were insufficiently incorporated into the decision-making process. The resulting dynamic fostered the gradual accumulation of constraint residuals, feeding a spiral of violence that gave rise to the period known as the Black Decade. This case thus illustrates the dynamic captured by Hypothesis 1: the mismatch between a high political index and a predominantly reactive mode of decision-making.

5.2 The Arab Spring (2011): Breakdown under an Explicit Solver

Faced with social protest movements, particularly in Tunisia and Egypt, the authorities initially favored coercive and reactive responses that may be likened to an explicit decision-making mode. These measures were implemented in systems already highly constrained, characterized by strong centralization of power, limited institutional capacity for self-correction, and the gradual accumulation of social tensions. The combination of structural vulnerabilities and reactive decisions contributed to a rapid accumulation of constraint residuals, precipitating unexpected political ruptures. This case illustrates Hypothesis 1, according to which a high political index combined with an explicit solver increases the risk of rupture.

5.3 The Algerian Hirak (2019): Stabilization through Strategic Reorientation

Despite a high political index and marked institutional rigidity, the underlying decision-making logic gradually evolved from a primarily coercive response toward a more implicit mode.

In the wake of the Black Decade, both the authorities and civil society favored peaceful and de-escalatory tactics that helped avoid direct and violent confrontation. The institutional response combined temporization, procedural adjustment, and internal reorganization within the ruling structure, including the replacement of certain leading figures and the delayed organization of the electoral process.

This reorientation limited the immediate accumulation of constraint residuals and enabled a degree of relative stabilization. The case illustrates Hypothesis 3, according to which a more cautious and integrative strategy can prevent immediate rupture. However, the underlying issue of regime change was not resolved, since the system effectively regenerated itself. Structural tensions therefore remain in place and may fuel future crises by postponing the political transformation that had been expected.

5.4 The US–Israel–Iran Escalation (2023–2026): Hegemonic Constraint and Residual Drift

The period from 2023 to 2026, marked by intensifying tensions among the United States, Israel, and Iran, may be interpreted as an example of a system with a medium-high political index. In this type of configuration, the hegemonic power must navigate multiple constraints: alliance

commitments, respect for international law, regional stability, strategic deterrence, energy security, domestic public opinion, and the preservation of international credibility.

US foreign policy traditionally grounded in relatively implicit mechanisms—multilateral consultation, alliances, recourse to the UN framework, and gradual crisis management—has, in certain phases, shifted toward more explicit, unilateral, or coercive forms of action. This shift does not necessarily increase the index in the strict sense, but it may increase the constraint residual—that is, the gap between the decisions taken and the full set of constraints that the hegemonic system is expected to respect simultaneously.

Within the framework of the proposed analogy, more frequent reliance on an explicit decision-making mode may take the form of targeted strikes, strengthened sanctions, asymmetric diplomatic support, or limited military interventions. Such decisions may generate constraint drift, or “drift-off,” when the gap widens between proclaimed norms, institutional commitments, and actual practices. As of May 2026, this configuration appears to have increased regional instability in the Middle East and heightened the risk that new crises will spread.

This case therefore illustrates a dynamic distinct from the internal ruptures observed in certain authoritarian regimes. It does not involve direct institutional collapse, but rather the gradual accumulation of constraint residuals within a highly constrained hegemonic system. Table 1 summarizes the cases examined in terms of heuristic political index, dominant solver type, and observed trajectory. The values of k should be understood as ordinal and illustrative markers rather than empirically derived cardinal measures.

Table 1. *Comparative Summary of the Cases Studied*

<i>Case</i>	<i>Heuristic Political Index</i>	<i>Dominant Solver</i>	<i>Observed Trajectory</i>
Algeria’s Black Decade	Very high, $k \geq 3$	Explicit	Breakdown
Arab Spring (Tunisia and Egypt)	High, $k \geq 3$	Explicit	Breakdown
Algerian Hirak	High, $k \geq 3$	Explicit → Implicit	Relative stabilization
United States–Israel–Iran (2023–2026)	Medium-high, $k \approx 2$	Implicit → Explicit	Escalation / constraint drift

6. Discussion

6.1 Implications for the Theory and Practice of Governance

The “governance under constraints” framework offers a functional interpretation of political crises by linking the management of institutional constraints to the modes of decision-making mobilized by actors in power. In doing so, it establishes a heuristic bridge between structuralist approaches to complexity and dynamic analyses of decision-making processes under crisis conditions.

In this context, Jervis's (1997) work on systemic effects and complex interactions shows that political systems may generate nonlinear dynamics that are difficult to anticipate on the basis of individual behavior alone. Drezner (2008), for his part, highlights the role of institutional architectures and governance regimes in managing constraints and international crises. The present article extends this line of inquiry by offering a functional reading inspired by DAEs and centered on the fit between the degree of institutional constraint and the mode of decision-making.

From this perspective, a regime's vulnerability depends not only on structural rigidity but also on the degree of fit between the level of constraint to which the system is subject and the mode of governance adopted. The proposed framework highlights, in particular, the risks associated with reactive and coercive responses—emergency decrees, rapid repression, unilateral interventions—when these are applied to rigid, highly constrained systems. Even though the “political index” k does not possess a mathematically rigorous definition comparable to that of a DAE index, its heuristic use makes it possible to characterize the degree of interdependence, lock-in, and hierarchical structuring of institutional constraints.

To be sure, some highly constrained regimes may survive over long periods despite predominantly explicit modes of decision-making, especially when they possess favorable coercive, economic, or geopolitical resources. Conversely, relatively flexible systems may still experience rupture despite more integrative decision-making mechanisms. The framework proposed here is therefore intended less to establish systematic causal relations than to identify broad functional tendencies.

6.2 Toward a Parametric Reading of Rupture

Although it remains heuristic, this framework may open new avenues for thinking about political dynamics under constraint in a more fine-grained way. In this respect, several concepts drawn from DAEs may be used as conceptual tools. The constraint residual Φ may represent the gap between decisions actually taken and the institutional, social, or geopolitical constraints the system is expected to respect. Lagrange multipliers λ may be interpreted as mechanisms of pressure, stabilization, or compensation deployed to preserve coherence within a constrained system. As for stiffness, it should not be conflated with the political index. In this transposition, stiffness may instead be understood as the difficulty of dynamic adjustment when a rapid shock affects a highly constrained system. These notions make it possible to organize a comparative reading of political trajectories in times of crisis without claiming either direct measurement or predictive capacity.

7. Conclusion

This study offers a functional interpretation of political crises grounded in a heuristic analogy with DAE systems. Within this approach, the stability of a regime in times of crisis depends less on institutional rigidity alone than on the degree of fit between the level of constraint to which the system is subject and the mode of governance adopted.

The index k borrowed from the vocabulary of DAEs is not used here as a direct indicator of stiffness, but as a metaphor for the degree of interdependence, lock-in, and hierarchical organization of institutional constraints. The higher the political index, the more tightly

constraints are intertwined, the harder they are to disentangle, and the more likely they are to generate cascading effects when ignored or handled sequentially.

Within this analogy, a solver represents the mode of decision-making adopted by actors in power. An explicit solver corresponds to a reactive, sequential, and often coercive logic of decision. An implicit solver corresponds to an integrative and anticipatory logic that considers multiple constraints simultaneously.

The analysis suggests that explicit modes of decision-making may amplify imbalances when applied to highly constrained systems. In such cases, they favor the accumulation of constraint residuals, which may manifest themselves in the form of loss of legitimacy, normative drift, escalation, or institutional rupture. By contrast, implicit modes of decision-making may help preserve relative stability by integrating social, political, economic, and geopolitical constraints at an earlier stage.

The proposed framework remains exploratory, metaphorical, and non-predictive. It does not seek to transform political regimes into mathematical objects or to establish universal causal laws. Its main contribution is to promote a shared language between engineering and political science for conceptualizing crises as problems of dynamic constraint management. From this perspective, the decision-maker's "algorithmic competence," as defined above, emerges as a central element of institutional resilience.

Future research could deepen this analogy by further developing the concepts of constraint residual, institutional drift, and stabilizing pressure. It could also explore the construction of a more systematic typology of regimes according to their degree of institutional entanglement and their dominant mode of decision-making.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

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Data Availability

This study is based on a conceptual and comparative analysis of historical and contemporary cases. No original dataset was generated.

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